

IMPLEMENTATION NOTES FOR RESEARCHERS

Research involving human participants generally requires an informed consent form to be read, understood, and signed before their participation in a study may commence. Informed consent aims to ensure that participants are aware of a study’s purpose, procedures, potential risks, and their right to withdraw, while also providing the investigator with a clear mandate specifying what data may be collected, used, and shared. The following template is provided as a resource to assist researchers in preparing such participant consent forms for studies capturing human movement data, especially where data sharing may be a consideration.

This document is intended to be dynamic, evolving alongside changes in policy and regulation and expanding beyond the jurisdictions currently represented. We welcome correspondence to guide future revisions.

This document provides guidance for adapting the following informed consent template to specific jurisdictions and studies. Researchers **should always consult with their local legal counsel and ethics committees** to ensure they appropriately adapt this template to comply with local requirements.

How to use this template:

Text **highlighted in yellow** (e.g. **[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]**) clearly indicates which sections require attention. **Review and edit the instructions for researchers and/or sample text** (text highlighted in grey) to adapt the form to your specific study and jurisdiction. Remove any subcomponents marked as **[INCLUDE ONLY IF APPLICABLE]** that do **not** apply to your study (e.g. Special Categories of Data and Samples section). In general, all highlighted and coloured text should be confirmed, adapted, or removed before submission.

Each section is labelled as either **[GENERAL]** or **[RECOMMENDED]**, as follows:

Section Legend

[GENERAL]	These sections address general requirements common to major data protection frameworks. Researchers must include, review and adapt as appropriate these sections for all studies.
[RECOMMENDED]	These sections are often not explicitly required by major data protection frameworks, but are highly recommended for studies where data sharing is a consideration . These sections are optional but strongly encouraged .

Carefully read and consider the informational jurisdiction-specific boxes, which always sit directly below the section that requires adaptation. If your jurisdiction requires additional clarifications due to your lab’s location and/or your study’s participant population, be sure to **incorporate these points accordingly before deleting the jurisdiction-specific boxes**. For jurisdictions not covered by the current version of this document, this template may be used as a guide to develop jurisdiction-appropriate consent materials, though we recommend consulting with your local ethics board or regulatory authority to ensure compliance. For example, for the UK: Post-Brexit UK GDPR applies, similar to EU GDPR but separate regime; for Canada: PIPEDA federally, provincial laws (e.g. Quebec Law 25) may apply; for Japan: APPI, adequacy decision with EU.

Jurisdiction Legend

[EU]	Specific to EU/EEA (General Data Protection Regulation; GDPR)
[US]	Specific to US (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act; HIPAA/Common Rule)
[CH]	Specific to Switzerland (Federal Act on Data Protection; FADP)
[AU]	Specific to Australia (Privacy Act 1988)

Translate the form if your participants' first language is not English.

Test the form's readability (e.g. through consumer/patient/stakeholder engagement groups). Aim for plain language appropriate for your study cohort(s).

Have the form reviewed by your institutional legal counsel / Data Protection Officer.

Have the form reviewed by your local ethics committee / Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Remove these implementation notes (first three pages) before including this form as part of your ethics application submission.

Key Jurisdictional Considerations

Always consult local legal counsel and ethics committees

European Union / European Economic Area (GDPR)

- Consent must be freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous (Article 7)
- Must identify the Data Controller and Data Protection Officer
- Must specify data retention period or criteria
- Must inform participants about rights: access, rectification, erasure, restriction, portability, objection
- Must specify international data transfer mechanisms (adequacy decisions, Standard Contractual Clauses, etc.)
- Must provide contact of the national supervisory authority
- Age of consent varies by member state (13-16 years); parental or legal guardian consent required below threshold

United States (HIPAA / Common Rule)

- HIPAA Authorization requires study-specific purposes; "unspecified future research" may be invalid
- Common Rule within the Code of Federal Regulations (45 CFR 46) governs federally-funded research
- Broad consent provisions (45 CFR 46.116(d)) may apply but are rarely used
- IRB waiver of authorisation may be needed for broad data sharing
- HIPAA does not permit data deletion (unlike GDPR)
- State laws may impose additional requirements (e.g. California Consumer Privacy Act)

Switzerland (FADP)

- New Federal Act on Data Protection (nFADP) effective from September 2023
- Human Research Act (HRA) governs research-specific requirements, superseding the FADP where the two overlap in human research contexts
- "General Consent" model widely accepted for broad research use
- Must specify destination countries for international transfers
- Switzerland has EU adequacy decision - data can flow freely to/from EU members

Australia (Privacy Act 1988)

- Privacy Act 1988 and Australian Privacy Principles (APPs) govern personal information handling
- National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007, updated 2018) provides research ethics framework
- Human Research Ethics Committees (HRECs) review and approve research involving human participants
- APP 8 requires consent or reasonable steps for cross-border disclosure of personal information
- Health information has additional protections under state/territory health records legislation
- OAIC (Office of the Australian Information Commissioner) provides guidance on research use of personal information
- No EU adequacy decision - data transfers to/from EU require appropriate safeguards

References

- EU GDPR: Regulation (EU) 2016/679
- US HIPAA Privacy Rule: 45 CFR Part 164
- US Common Rule: 45 CFR Part 46
- Swiss FADP: Federal Act on Data Protection (SR 235.1)
- Swiss HRA: Human Research Act (SR 810.30)
- ICO (UK): Guide to the UK GDPR
- EDPB: Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679
- AU Privacy Act: Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)
- AU APPs: Australian Privacy Principles (Schedule 1 to the Privacy Act 1988)

Disclaimer

This document does not constitute legal advice. The authors of this template accept no responsibility or liability for its use. Each researcher holds the responsibility to ensure that their consent form complies with all applicable laws, regulations, and institutional requirements. Researchers should consult with their local ethics committee, Institutional Review Board, legal counsel, and/or Data Protection Officer before use.

[INSTITUTION NAME]

Information and Consent Form for the Collection, Use and/or Sharing of Health-Related Data

[STUDY NAME]

PART A: INFORMATION SHEET

Dear Participant,

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

Our ability to understand human movement and advance treatments for movement-related conditions has progressed significantly in recent decades. These advances are the result of medical and scientific research in which researchers and participants have actively collaborated and shared data/findings. An important part of this research relies on sharing health-related data, including movement recordings, laboratory analyses, imaging data, and associated clinical information.

[Describe your specific study, including the motivation and its aims.]

This document explains how you can contribute to research by allowing your data to be used and potentially shared with other researchers, and provides information about data protection and your rights.

1. How Can You Contribute to Research? [GENERAL]

By signing this consent form, you agree to participate in this study and make your data available for research purposes. This includes data collected during the study, as well as any follow-up assessments.

Your consent is voluntary. Your decision to participate in the current study has no effect on your medical treatment or clinical care. You may withdraw your consent [ADAPT TO YOUR JURISDICTION] at any time / within a specified time window [indicate time window] without having to provide a reason and without any negative consequences.

[EU] Under GDPR, consent must be withdrawable "at any time" (Article 7(3)), and withdrawal must be as easy as giving consent. You cannot impose a time window restriction on withdrawal. However, you should explain that withdrawal does not affect the lawfulness of processing carried out before withdrawal, and that data already anonymised or included in published results may not be retrievable.

[US] Under HIPAA, participants may revoke their authorisation at any time, but revocation is not retroactive - it does not apply to data already used or disclosed in reliance on the authorisation. Under the Common Rule, the right to withdraw is standard, but specific study protocols (particularly clinical trials with FDA involvement) may specify practical deadlines by which withdrawal must be communicated to be effective for certain purposes. Consult your IRB for study-specific requirements.

[CH] Under the Human Research Act (HRA), participants may withdraw consent at any time. Withdrawal does not affect data processing that occurred lawfully before withdrawal. Participants must be informed of the practical consequences of withdrawal, e.g. that their data will not be used in future research, but that data already collected cannot be deleted before the end of the mandatory retention period (min. 10 years after study completion, as required by the Human Research Act). As with GDPR, imposing a time window on the right to withdraw would be inconsistent with Swiss data protection principles.

[AU] Under the Privacy Act 1988, consent may be withdrawn at any time. There is no provision for imposing a time window restriction. You should explain that withdrawal does not affect data already used in research or de-identified prior to withdrawal, and that data already deposited in public repositories may have been accessed by other researchers.

2. What Data Will Be Collected? **[GENERAL]**

The following types of data may be collected:

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

[Make sure you inform participants of the burdens associated with participation, not just what data will be collected; i.e. specify the level of effort required from the participant to provide each type of data.]

- Demographic information (e.g. age, sex, relevant medical conditions) - requires completing a short questionnaire
- Clinical assessments and medical history - requires an in-person appointment and interview with the study clinician
- Movement data (e.g. motion capture, accelerometer data, gait analysis) - requires wearing sensors or markers during movement tasks
- Video and/or photographic recordings (de-identified where possible, e.g. facial blurring or removal of facial features, tattoos, scars, and other identifying body markings) - requires being filmed or photographed during assessments
- Medical imaging (e.g. MRI, CT, X-ray, ultrasound) - requires attending an imaging session and may expose the participant to radiation

3. How Are Your Data Protected? **[GENERAL]**

Your data will be stored securely and protected in accordance with applicable legal requirements. Only authorised personnel will have access to your identifiable data.

Before your data are used for research or shared with other researchers, they will be:

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

- **Pseudonymised:** All personal identifiers (name, date of birth, etc.) will be replaced with a code. The key linking the code to your identity will be kept secure and separate from the research data. Researchers using the pseudonymised data cannot identify you without the key.
- OR
- **Anonymised:** The link between the data and your identity will be permanently removed, making re-identification impossible.

You have rights regarding your personal data, including the right to access your data and to request correction of inaccurate information.

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC JURISDICTION]

[The process for exercising these rights and any limitations that apply may vary depending on your jurisdiction. Example jurisdiction-specific clarifications have been provided below. Adapt this section accordingly.]

[EU/GDPR] Under GDPR, you have specific rights regarding your personal data, including the right to access, rectify, erase, and restrict processing of your data. The legal basis for processing your data is your explicit consent (Article 6(1)(a) and Article 9(2)(a) GDPR). You may exercise these rights by contacting the Data Protection Officer listed at the end of this document.

[US] Under the HIPAA Privacy Rule, you have the right to access and obtain a copy of your protected health information (PHI), and to request amendments to inaccurate information. You also have the right to receive an accounting of certain disclosures of your PHI. To exercise these rights, contact the research team or the institution's Privacy Officer. Note that these rights apply to identifiable health information; they do not apply to de-identified data or data used under an IRB waiver of authorisation.

[CH] Under the FADP, you have the right to request information about whether your personal data is being processed, to access your data, and to request rectification of inaccurate data. You also have the right to request deletion of your data, subject to legal retention requirements and research exemptions. To exercise these rights, contact the research team. There is one important exception: if the data was collected within a research project or a clinical trial, the data cannot be deleted early since this would contradict data retention requirements.

[AU] Under the Privacy Act 1988, you have the right to access personal information held about you (APP 12) and to request correction of inaccurate, out-of-date, or misleading information (APP 13). To exercise these rights, contact the research team. The institution must respond to access requests within a reasonable period. If your correction request is refused, you may request that a statement of the correction sought be associated with your data.

4. Risks and Benefits **[GENERAL]**

Risks

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

Participation in this study involves minimal risk to you personally. The primary risk associated with data collection and sharing is the potential for unintended disclosure of your personal information. To minimise this risk, your data will be pseudonymised before being shared with other researchers.

[Describe any risks specific to your study, including physical risks associated with data collection procedures (e.g. discomfort associated with biological sampling), and any psychological risks (e.g. discomfort arising from questions about medical history).]

Benefits

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

You will not receive direct personal benefit from participation in this study. However, your contribution may benefit future patients and the broader scientific community by advancing our understanding of human movement science.

[Describe the expected scientific or societal benefit.]

Liability and Insurance

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

This study is covered by [INSTITUTION NAME]'s institutional liability insurance (Policy No. [XXXXX], held with [INSURER NAME]). In the event that you suffer harm as a direct result of your participation in this study, you may be entitled to compensation; please contact [NAME, EMAIL, PHONE]. This coverage applies to harm arising directly from study procedures and does not affect your statutory rights.

[INCLUDE AND ADAPT IF APPLICABLE TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

[If your study involves a vulnerable population (e.g. persons with movement disabilities, older adults, or those with cognitive impairments), you are generally required to additionally explain what measures are in place to protect their rights and welfare, and why the research could not be conducted with a less vulnerable group.]

[EU/GDPR] Under GDPR Article 13(2)(d), participants must be informed of any risks associated with the processing of their personal data, particularly where special category data such as health data is involved. Ensure your description of data-related risks is specific and meaningful - vague statements are insufficient. There is no mandatory insurance requirement under GDPR, but your ethics committee will likely require evidence that risks have been identified, assessed, and minimised.

[US] Under the Common Rule (45 CFR 46.116(b)), a description of foreseeable risks and discomforts, and a description of any benefits to participants or others, are mandatory elements of informed consent - their omission can invalidate IRB approval. Under HIPAA, participants must also be informed of the potential risk of a privacy breach. Ensure your IRB-approved protocol specifies both the risks of the procedures involved and the risks associated with data handling and sharing.

[CH] Under the HRA, research projects must be categorised according to the level of risk they pose to participants, and this categorisation determines the applicable ethics review procedure. In principle, research projects subject to the HRA must be covered by insurance for harm caused to participants, with the exception of certain low-risk Category A studies. Confirm your study's risk category and insurance requirements with your ethics committee via the BASEC platform before use.

[AU] The National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research requires that participants be clearly informed of the risks, burdens, and potential benefits of participation. Under the 2023 National Statement, risks are assessed on a continuum from lower to higher risk, and must be justified by the potential benefits of the research. Burdens and inconvenience to participants are considered separately from risks. HRECs will scrutinise this section closely. There is no single national statutory insurance requirement for all human research in Australia; requirements vary by study type, jurisdiction, and institution. Commercially sponsored clinical trials are subject to mandatory insurance requirements that vary by state and territory. For all other research, institutional indemnity arrangements are standard practice — confirm coverage with your institution before use and specify the arrangements here.

5. Who May Use Your Data? **[GENERAL]**

Your **[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]** pseudonymised or anonymised data may be used by authorised researchers for research projects:

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

- Within this institution
- In collaboration with other public research institutions (e.g. universities, hospitals)
- In collaboration with private entities (e.g. pharmaceutical or medical device companies)
- Both within your country of residence and internationally

You may separately indicate your preferences regarding certain types of data sharing (such as collaborations with commercial entities) in the consent section below.

All research projects using your data must be approved by an appropriate **[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY] ethics committee or Institutional Review Board (IRB).**

6. International Data Transfers **[GENERAL]**

Your data may be transferred to researchers in other countries. When data are transferred internationally, appropriate safeguards are implemented to ensure your data remain protected, which may include:

- **Legal agreements** requiring recipients to protect your data to an equivalent standard
- **Technical measures** such as encryption and access controls
- **Institutional review** to verify the recipient's data protection practices

Countries to which your data may be transferred include:

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

[List specific countries or regions, e.g. EU/EEA member states, United States, etc.]

[INCLUDE ONLY IF APPLICABLE].

Some countries to which your data may be transferred do not have data protection laws equivalent to those in your country. Researchers receiving your data will be bound by contractual obligations to protect your data, and your data will only be shared with institutions that have agreed to appropriate data protection measures. However, you may not have the same legal remedies (i.e. rights) in those countries as you would at home.

[EU] Under GDPR Articles 44–49, data transfers to third countries require either an adequacy decision, appropriate safeguards (e.g. Standard Contractual Clauses, Binding Corporate Rules), or a derogation/exemption (such as explicit consent). Where relying on consent as a derogation, participants must be informed of the risks. Document your transfer impact assessment and ensure the chosen mechanism is appropriate for the nature and volume of data transferred.

[US] HIPAA-covered entities must ensure that any international transfers comply with the HIPAA Privacy Rule. If sharing PHI with international researchers, a Business Associate Agreement or other HIPAA-compliant mechanism may be required. Consider whether the recipient country's laws provide adequate protection or whether additional contractual safeguards are needed. State privacy laws (e.g. California CCPA/CPRA) may impose additional cross-border transfer requirements.

[CH] Under the revised FADP (nFADP), transfers to countries without adequate protection require appropriate safeguards or the data subject's explicit consent after being informed of the risks. Switzerland maintains its own list of countries with adequate protection, which largely aligns with EU adequacy decisions. For health-related research data, the HRA applies as the primary framework: ensure participant consent for future research use was obtained at the time of data collection (Art. 17 HRA), and verify that any transmission to foreign authorities or organisations complies with Art. 60 HRA.

[AU] Under APP 8, before disclosing personal information to an overseas recipient, you must either (a) take reasonable steps to ensure the recipient will not breach the APPs, or (b) obtain the individual's consent after informing them that APP 8.1 will not apply. This consent form uses approach (b). Ensure participants understand that overseas recipients may not be subject to Australian privacy laws and that redress under the Privacy Act 1988 may be limited. The OAIC recommends documenting your assessment of overseas recipients' privacy practices.

7. How Long Will Your Data Be Stored? **[GENERAL]**

Your data will be retained for as long as necessary to fulfill the research purposes specified in this document. **[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]** [Specify the exact duration or criteria, e.g. "at least XX years after the completion of the study" or "indefinitely for long-term research purposes".]

Anonymised data may be retained indefinitely as they can no longer be linked to you.

[EU] GDPR requires that you specify either a concrete retention period or the criteria used to determine it (Article 13(2)(a)). Vague statements like "as long as necessary" alone are insufficient — you must provide meaningful information. Research exemptions (Article 89) allow extended retention for scientific research purposes, but you must still justify the duration. Consider your institution's data retention policy and any funder requirements.

[US] HIPAA requires covered entities to retain PHI for six years from the date of creation or last effective date. The Common Rule does not specify retention periods, but many federal funders and institutions require retention of research data for a minimum period (commonly 3–7 years after study completion). FDA-regulated research may require longer retention. Check your institutional policy, funder requirements, and any applicable state laws.

[CH] HRA requires retention of research data for at least 10 years after study completion or after publication of results. This retention obligation takes precedence over any individual request for data deletion; i.e. the data must not be deleted before the end of that retention period, even if the participant withdraws consent and requests deletion of their data. The FADP requires that retention be proportionate to the research purpose. Ensure your stated retention period meets HRA minimums and is consistent with your institution's policies.

[AU] The Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research recommends retaining research data for at least five years after publication or study completion, and longer for clinical trials (at least 15 years). Some institutions and funders impose additional requirements. The Privacy Act requires that data not be kept longer than necessary, so you should justify extended retention by reference to research purposes.

8. Use of Data for Future Research **[RECOMMENDED]**

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

Your data may be used for future research projects that are not yet planned at the time of this consent. Such future research:

- Must be approved by an ethics committee or IRB
- Must be related to human movement, health, or medical research
- Will use only pseudonymised or anonymised versions of your data

[US] Under the HIPAA Privacy Rule, authorisation for "unspecified future research" may be considered overly broad. US institutions receiving data under this consent may need to obtain IRB waivers of authorisation or implement additional study-specific authorisations depending on their institutional policies.

9. Deposit in Public Research Repositories **[RECOMMENDED]**

To maximise the scientific value of your contribution and support reproducible research, a de-identified copy of your data may be deposited in publicly accessible research repositories (e.g. institutional data archives, discipline-specific databases). This copy is processed to remove or modify identifying information and **[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]** is kept separate from any record linking your data to you held by the study team OR no record linking your data to you exists.

Data in public repositories:

- Will NOT contain direct identifiers (name, date of birth, contact information)
- Will have potentially identifying features removed or modified (e.g. blurring or removal of facial features, tattoos, scars, and other identifying body markings)
- May be subject to access controls requiring researchers to agree to data use terms

You may separately indicate whether you consent to your data being deposited in a public repository in the consent section below.

10. **[INCLUDE AND ADAPT IF APPLICABLE TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]** Special Categories of Data and Samples **[GENERAL]**

[Include and adapt this section accordingly if your study involves any special categories of data and/or samples (e.g. medical records, genetic data, biological samples, mental health data, data from minors or vulnerable populations). Such categories attract additional legal and ethical requirements beyond those covered in this form for human movement data. You are responsible for identifying and complying with the specific requirements applicable to your study, jurisdiction, and ethics committee.]

11. Incidental Findings **[GENERAL]**

Research conducted with your data will generally not reveal individual information relevant to your personal health. However, in rare cases, research findings might be relevant for your health. In such cases, you may be contacted, *provided you have indicated your willingness to be contacted* (see consent section below).

12. Costs, Financial Considerations, and Funding **[GENERAL]**

There are no additional costs to you for participating in this study. You will not receive direct financial benefit from the use of your data. Research using your data may eventually lead to the development of commercial products or services, but you will not share in any profits from such developments.

[INCLUDE AND ADAPT ONLY IF APPLICABLE TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

[If participants will be reimbursed, include or adapt one of the following as appropriate.]

You will not receive any payment or reimbursement for your participation.

OR

You will receive reimbursement for reasonable travel and out-of-pocket expenses incurred as a result of your participation in this study. [Specify amount or basis, e.g. "up to CHF/EUR/USD per visit" or "in accordance with your actual costs upon presentation of receipts"].

AND/OR

You will receive a participation compensation fee of [Specify amount and currency] in recognition of your time and effort.

This study is funded by: [ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY] [List main funding sources, e.g. institutional funding, national research grant, industry sponsor.]

[CH] Under the Human Research Ordinance (HRO), disclosure of the main sources of financing and any agreements between the sponsor, third parties, and the project leader is a mandatory requirement. Specify all funding sources and financial arrangements here before submitting to your ethics committee via BASEC.

[AU] The NHMRC National Statement requires that any conflicts of interest, including financial relationships between researchers and funders, be disclosed to participants. While there is no explicit statutory requirement to list all funding sources, HRECs will expect transparency about commercial sponsorship or funding arrangements that could influence the research. Confirm requirements with your HREC.

13. Withdrawal of Consent [GENERAL]

You may withdraw your consent at any time by contacting the research team (see contact information below). Withdrawal has no effect on your medical care or your participation in ongoing studies.

Upon withdrawal:

- Your data will no longer be made available for new research projects
- Data already included in ongoing analyses or published results may not be removable
- Data already shared with other researchers in anonymised form cannot be retrieved
- Data deposited in public repositories may have already been downloaded by other researchers and cannot be retrieved

[EU] Under GDPR Article 17, you have the right to request erasure of your personal data. However, this right may be limited where processing is necessary for scientific research purposes and erasure would seriously impair the study research objectives (Article 17(3)(d)).

14. Contact Information [GENERAL]

[ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY]

For questions about this research or to withdraw consent:

[Principal Investigator Name, Institution, Email, Phone]

For questions about data protection:

[Privacy Officer/Data Protection Officer Name, Institution, Email]

For concerns about your rights as a research participant:

[Ethics Committee/IRB Contact Information]

Supervisory Authority for data protection complaints:

[Name and contact for relevant authority, e.g. your national Data Protection Authority (EU/UK), HHS Office for Civil Rights (US), OAIC (AU), FDPIC (CH)]

PART B: DECLARATION OF CONSENT

For the Collection, Use and/or Sharing of Health-Related Data

[STUDY NAME]

Participant Name (Surname, First Name)	Date of Birth
_____	_____

I confirm that: [GENERAL]

- I have read and understood the information sheet (Part A) regarding the use of my data for research purposes.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and have received satisfactory answers.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw my consent at any time without providing a reason and without any negative consequences.
- I was informed about the risks and benefits of participation in this study.
- I understand that my data will be pseudonymised or anonymised before being used for research.
- I understand that my data may be used by researchers at this institution and other institutions, including in other countries.
- I understand that research projects using my data must be approved by [ADAPT TO YOUR SPECIFIC STUDY] an ethics committee or IRB.

Primary Consent [GENERAL]

I consent to the use of my health-related data for research purposes as described in the information sheet:

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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Optional Consents [RECOMMENDED]

The following are optional. You may participate in the research even if you do not consent to these items:

a) Future unspecified research: I consent to the use of my pseudonymised data for future research projects not yet planned, subject to ethics committee approval.

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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b) Public repository deposit: I consent to the deposit of my anonymised/de-identified data in public research repositories accessible to qualified researchers worldwide.

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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c) Video/image data sharing:

[INCLUDE ONLY IF APPLICABLE] I consent to my video or photographic data being shared for research purposes after de-identification has been applied (e.g. blurring or removal of facial features, tattoos, scars, and other identifying body markings).

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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[INCLUDE ONLY IF APPLICABLE - Note: Sharing of identifiable video or photographic data requires explicit ethics committee approval and must comply with applicable legal and jurisdictional requirements. Include this option only where your ethics approval explicitly permits identifiable data sharing.] I consent to my video or photographic data being shared for research purposes in identifiable form (i.e. without de-identification).

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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d) Recontact for incidental findings: I agree to be recontacted if research reveals findings that may be relevant for my health.

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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e) Commercial research collaborations: I consent to the use of my data in research projects conducted in collaboration with commercial entities (e.g. pharmaceutical companies).

<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Signature: _____
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Signatures

Participant:

Place, Date _____	Signature _____
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Legal Representative: [INCLUDE ONLY IF APPLICABLE]

Place, Date _____	Name & Relationship _____	Signature _____
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Person obtaining consent:

Place, Date _____	Printed Name _____	Signature _____
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